

Influence Of Wind Speed And Direct Solar Irradiance On The Performance Of Photovoltaic Modules

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Abstract

The aim of present work is to investigate the performance of photovoltaic modules (PV) influence by wind speed and direct solar irradiance in Saudi Arabia. These two parameters have a significant effect on the performance of PV module. In the present work experimental set up, one unit of the PV module was examined with change of wind speed and direct solar irradiance in two different locations in Saudi Arabia. Each location has its private weather data. First location is Al-Baha city which locate in the southwest of Saudi Arabia. The second location is Al-Jubailcity in the east of Saudi Arabia. This variety of the two locations gives a real prediction about the present work results for all regions in Saudi Arabia. The efficiency of the PV module, operating ambient temperatures and module temperatures are investigated with change of wind speed and direct solar irradiance. Through the present investigation the wind speed range is between 2 and 11 m/s. In the other hand direct solar irradiance changed from 300 to 1000 W/m². The results show that with the increase of wind speed the module temperature decreases which leads to increase in its efficiency. In addition part of direct solar irradiance converted into electrical energy, and the rest is converted into heat energy. Therefore, the heat energy generated by the PV panel increases its operating PV module temperature. Consequently, this leads to decrease of module efficiency with the increase of solar irradiation. The present results are compatible with previous work results and show the important of wind speed and direct solar irradiance in the PV modules performance.

Introduction

Energy is so progressed, and economic growth is one of the world's most crucial issues. Availability of non-renewable energy is bounded, and their long-term adverse effects on the natural balance of planet earth, underline the growth and development of renewable energy needs. Solar energy is the most popular to solve the problem of non-renewable energy among all the renewable energy. PV panel is a device that directly converts solar energy into electricity without any equipment. Besides, PV system generates electrical energy without producing environmental pollution and emissions of greenhouse [1, 2]. PV is also an interesting energy; it is renewable, abundant, silent and environmentally friendly, and can supply electricity in different applications. While the wind doesn't give the sun's light rays any extra oomph when powering panels, the effect of wind is a boost in PV modules efficiency. The efficiency of the module has dependency on the environmental parameters [3]. Meteorological data such as solar radiation, ambient temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed are accepted as dependable and widely variable renewable energy sources [4, 5]. The direct irradiance received on a plane normal to the sun over the total solar spectrum is defined as direct normal irradiance (DNI). DNI is an essential component of global irradiance, especially under cloudless conditions, and represents the solar resource that can be used by various types of PV modules [6]. A photovoltaic (PV) module's rated efficiency helps a PV system designer compare modules from different manufacturers, as well as estimate how much electrical energy the module will produce. However, accurate energy yield predictions also need to take into account the fact that the as-installed efficiency will depend on the module operating temperatures, irradiance levels, irradiance spectra, wind speeds and incident angles, among other factors. This causes the actual efficiency to be different than the rated efficiency [7]. Lot of research have been done to increase the efficiency of the solar modules; like anti reflecting coatings, glass covers with least absorptivity, dust repulsive coatings and photovoltaic thermal hybrid system. Efficiency can also be increased by the use of heat exchangers using a specific fluid. This fluid can be used for other purposes. But due to high cost and complicated design they are not used [8, 9]. The present work aims to investigate the effect of wind speed and direct normal irradiation in the performance of PV modules.

1. Experimental set up

Figure (1) shows the present work experimental setup which is conducted in two different locations. First location is Al-Baha city which locate in the southwest of Saudi Arabia.

The other one is Al-Jubail city in the east of Saudi Arabia. The longitudinal and latitudinal coordinate of these locations is 20.518 N 41.665 E and 27.13 N 49.534 E respectively.

Figure (1): The present work experimental setup

1.1 General view

The present work set up consist of a solar PV module of type TPS-12-5 faces to the sun and Arduino Uno board microcontroller attached to it In addition two types of a temperature sensors is used to measure the ambient temperature and module temperature. LCD screen display these measurements by use microcontroller. Thus user can effectively monitor solar parameters using this system. Figure (2) shows the schematic diagram of the present work setup.

Figure (2): Schematic diagram for the present work experimental setup

1.2 Measuring instruments

1.2.1 Wind speed measurement

A professional digital anemometer shown in figure(3) is used to measure the wind speed. It has the following features:

- a low battery indicator
- Can be connected with computer for real time data uploading functions
- Precisely measuring and it can store up to 50,000 groups of data
- Helps to measure the wind temperature, humidity, wind speed, and air volume
- It has the functions of reading hold, maximum, minimum, etc.

Its main specifications are summarized in the following table:

Wind Speed Range	0-30m/s
Resolution	0.1m/s
Resolution	-10~45°C

Figure (3): Digital anemometer to measure wind speed

1.2.2 Direct solar irradiance measurement

Solar irradiance coming directly from the sun is measured by a pyrheliometer which is shown in figure (4). The SI units of irradiance are watts per square metre (W/m^2). Traditionally pyrheliometers were mainly used for climatological research and weather monitoring purposes, however recent worldwide interest in solar energy has also led to an increased interest in pyrheliometers. The all-digital DR30-D1 pyrheliometer is used which offers the highest accuracy and highest data availability. The Hukseflux Sensor Manager software provides a user interface for communication between a PC and digital Hukseflux pyrheliometers with a Modbus interface. A more in-depth discussion on how pyrheliometers work can be found in the book by Vignola et al. [10].

Figure (4): a pyrheliometer to measure direct solar irradiance

1.2.3 Ambient temperature measurement

LM35 temperature sensor shown in figure (2) is used to measure ambient temperature. The LM35 series are accurate integrated-circuit temperature sensors, whose output voltage is linearly proportional to the ambient temperature. The LM35 does not require any external calibration or trimming to provide typical accuracies of $\pm 1/4^\circ\text{C}$ at room temperature and $\pm 3/4^\circ\text{C}$ over a full -55 to $+150^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range.

Figure (5): LM35 temperature sensor

1.2.4 PV module temperature measurement

Waterproof Temperature Sensor DS18B20 is used to measure cell temperature. As shown in figure (6) the Waterproof Temperature Sensor DS18B20 is the waterproof version of the DS18B20 sensor. Which is preferred to use when you need to measure something far away, or in wet conditions. While the sensor is rated up to 125°C the jacket softens at around 80°C . These 1-wire digital temperature sensors are fairly precise ($\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ over much of the range). They work great with any microcontroller using a single digital pin, and you can even connect multiple ones to the same pin.

Figure (6): DS18B20 temperature sensor

3. Result and discussion

In this section the data output from the present work investigation for the two locations was analyzed in detailed and discussed briefly. Also, the variation of results for the two locations are noticed and explained.

3.1 Data analysis in the two locations

Figure (7) shows the change of direct solar radiation with the time through the all measuring period. It varied from 500 to 1000 W/m^2 in Al-Baha city and from 300 to 980 W/m^2 in Al-Jubail city. While, the range of the wind speed through investigation time is shown in figure (8). The wind speed changed from 3 to 6 m/s and 2 to 11 m/s in Al-Baha and Al-Jubail respectively. Figure (9) shows the variation of ambient temperature through investigation time. Minimum ambient temperature is 16.5 °C in both two cities while the maximum value is 22°C in Al-Baha and 30.5 °C in Al-Jubail. PV module temperature in Al-Baha changes from 18 °C to 24°C and from 18 °C to 32 °C in Al-Jubail. The change of PV module temperature is illustrated in detail in figure (10). Finally, figure (11) shows the calculated values of PV module efficiency through the present work, which moves from 9% to 14 % in both cities. But, it is clear from all the previous figures that the present work results in Al-Baha is more stable and homogenous than Al-Jubail. This reflect that A-Baha weather is more suitable for all renewable energies applications.

Figure (7): The change of the direct normal solar irradiation through investigation time

Figure (8): The range of the wind speed through investigation time

Figure (9): The variation of ambient temperature through investigation time

Figure (10): The variation of PV module temperature through investigation time

Figure (11): The PV module efficiency through investigation time

3.2 Effect of wind speed

One of the main purpose of the present work is to study the influence of wind speed on the PV module performance. Figure (12) and Figure (13) show that with increase of wind speed, the operating ambient temperature and PV module temperature decreased. This trend is happened in the two locations but with different rate due to the effect of weather. This action is reflected on PV module performance especially in the operating efficiency. Figure (14) shows the relation between wind speed and PV module efficiency. It is clear that efficiency increases with the increase of wind speed in the two cities.

Figure (12): Effect of wind speed on operating ambient temperature

Figure (13): Effect of wind speed on PV module temperature

Figure (14): Effect of wind speed on operating efficiency

3.3. Effect of direct solar irradiance

The other important parameter in the current work is the effect direct solar irradiance in PV module performance. Figure (15) shows the variations in the output efficiency with direct solar radiation for Al-Baha and Al-Jubail cities. As the direct solar radiation affects the power it also affects the outcome efficiency of the PV module. The increase in direct solar radiation intensity is followed by an increase in the PV module temperature which eliminates the produced current and then reduces the power and at the end affects the efficiency and reduces it. This is in good agreement with [11]. The best solution for this problem is by converting the PV system to a PVT (*Photovoltaic thermal collectors*) system as reference [12][13] results clarified.

Figure (15): Effect of direct solar irradiance on operating efficiency

4. Conclusions

The present work investigation shows the influence of wind speed and direct solar irradiance on the performance of photovoltaic modules in Al-Baha and Al-Jubail cities in the southwest and east of Saudi Arabia respectively. The results show that with the increase of wind speed the module temperature decreases which leads to increase in its efficiency. In addition part of direct solar irradiance converted into electrical energy, and the rest is converted into heat energy. Therefore, the heat energy generated by the PV panel is increased in its operating PV module temperature. Consequently, this leads to decrease of module efficiency with the increase of solar irradiance. The results have the same trend in the two cities with different rates due to the weather effect. The present results are compatible with previous work results and show the important of wind speed and direct solar irradiance in the PV modules performance. In addition the present investigation suggest that it may be converting the PV system to a PVT (Photovoltaic thermal collectors) system to overcome the problem of increase of PV module temperature with the increase of direct solar irradiance.

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